

SSHOC

social sciences & humanities open cloud

Repositories and Beyond

Analysis of Survey for
SSHOC Organisations

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Abstract: The report analyses the results of a survey targeted at various SSHOC organisations to gain insight into the SSHOC trust landscape and different kinds of certification solutions applicable to different data services and repositories.

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Executive Summary

This report forms part of the overall body of work conducted by the SSHOC Task 8.2 *Trust & Quality Assurance, Impact* team which was tasked with examining the trust landscape of organisations participating in SSHOC and from the wider SSH domain. This report will examine the results of a survey targeted at organisations within the SSHOC community which offer services covering data and/or metadata. The survey was conducted in the summer of 2021. Areas examined by the survey include the type of data and/or metadata stored by the organisations, the support (and wider data) services offered by the organisations, certification status, data discovery provision and availability of repository information, amongst others.

The results highlight the diversity of the trust landscape and illustrate the differences between SSH repositories and wider data service providers. The results also highlight potential differences between certified and non-certified repositories in the availability of policies and documentation. Differing interpretations of policies and the variation in the terminology related to data integrity suggests that further work is needed to achieve a community consensus on the definitions of services and service components and the minimum acceptable level of information that data-holding organisations should provide to users and other stakeholders.

The plurality of data-holding organisations across the SSH landscape raises the issue of whether certification and/or assessment solutions are needed for wider data service providers that do not fit the 'traditional data repository' model, thus being ineligible for CoreTrustSeal certification.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
PID	Persistent Identifier
ROR	Research Organization Registry
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
TDR	Trusted Digital Repository
URN	Uniform Resource Name
VLO	Virtual Language Observatory

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1. Introduction

The results presented in this report form part of the overall body of work carried out in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC)¹ Task 8.2 Trust & Quality Assurance, Impact. The aim of Task 8.2 is to examine the trust landscape of SSHOC organisations and to gain insight into the kinds of certification solutions applicable to different data services and repositories. To this end, SSHOC T8.2 designed a survey targeted at SSHOC organisations that offer services around research data and metadata in any part of the research data lifecycle.

The organisations were contacted via email and a common communication platform set up for the project. Some partners shared the link to the survey on their social media accounts (see Appendix 1 for more details on the data collection and methodology and Appendix 2 for the questionnaire).

The number of responses (18 from 14 unique organisations) does not allow for the generalisation of results to the wider Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) community, but it does provide an overview of the similarities and differences between the different organisations. In addition to the survey, SSHOC T8.2 is examining the features of a wide range of SSHOC repositories through desk research, the results of which will be presented in a separate, forthcoming report.

In this report, we will examine the survey responses and present our conclusions based on the findings. The results are grouped into sections focusing on: Data, Metadata and Support; Certification, Data Discovery, Metadata Provision and Citation; Policies, Licences and Legal Information; and Preservation, Technical Infrastructure and Data Integrity. These sections are followed by discussion and conclusions.

¹ SSHOC Project: <https://sshopencloud.eu/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

2. Foreword on the Sample

The survey respondents were from a diverse group of organisations with differences in organisational structure (and purposes), types of data held and the technical infrastructure employed. For the purposes of this report, respondents have been grouped into two main categories: repositories and organisations.

The definition (of a repository) that was utilised to create this distinction is as follows:

“...organizations that preserve, manage, and provide access to digital research data in a variety of formats. A repository must have sufficient control and rights to ensure the digital material are authentic, reliable, accessible and usable also for the long term”²

Based on the above definition, 11 of the 14 respondents could be classed as repositories. Of the remaining three organisations, two of them would be classed as registries (or data service providers). The one remaining organisation was a research foundation which outsourced the storage of its data to a third-party repository, which did not participate in the survey.

² Kleemola et al. 2020.

3. Results

3.1 Metadata, Data and Support

Before this section begins in earnest, it is important to note that we will only be reporting on the data and metadata stored by the 11 repositories in Section 3.1.1. Whilst the two registries in our sample did store certain types of metadata, the authors of this report felt that their inclusion in the results detailed in this section would potentially obscure any comparisons that could be made between the organisations (particularly given the small sample size). This is due to the inherent differences in organisational structure and purpose. The third organisation did not store data and/or metadata, thus did not respond to related questions. Nevertheless, with the exception of the aforementioned organisations all 11 repositories reported that they held some form of data and stored some form of metadata in at least one schema (see table 1 below).

3.1.1 Metadata

Some of the responses provided by the repositories included reference to specific metadata schemas. Based on this information, it was subsequently decided that small scale desk research would be conducted to ascertain the metadata schemas used by the repositories in this sample (see table 1 below). The information gleaned from the desk research was based on the public information available on the repositories' website(s), re3data profiles (where applicable) and/or their CoreTrustSeal certification (in the case of certified repositories). The results are in line with the SSHOC Task 3.5 metadata format inventory.³

Metadata schemas used by repositories				
	Dublin Core	DDI	DataCite	PROV
Number of repositories	10	6	2	1

Table 1. Number of repositories (n=11) using a given metadata schema.

³ Broeder et al. 2019.

3.1.2 Data

Out of the 11 repositories surveyed all stated that they addressed data and/or metadata at the specialist level; one repository reported addressing it at both the generalist and specialist levels; and one repository stated that they could not say. The most common disciplines or domains among those that addressed (meta)data at a specialist level included social sciences and/or related fields (10 references among the responses), health or life sciences (5), humanities (3) and economics (3) (see table 2). Other domains mentioned included archaeology, environmental science and language and linguistics. The metadata schemas (Table 1) reflect these domains.

Data stored according to discipline					
	Social sciences	Health or life sciences	Humanities	Economics	Other disciplines
Number of repositories <i>(storing data relating to discipline)</i>	10	5	3	3	5

Table 2. Number of repositories (n=11) storing data according to discipline.⁴

Upon reviewing the responses from the repositories, it became apparent that there was considerable variation in the terminology used to refer to the different types of data that the repositories held (see Appendix 3). Whilst the authors fully acknowledge that this may be partly due to the wording of the questions, there were multiple instances where two or more repositories used different terms to refer to the same type of data. This is not overly surprising given the variation in repository domain(s) and their designated communities. It does, however, have implications for the development of standards and ongoing work examining the feasibility of descriptive, machine-actionable metadata about repositories and/or other institutions such as publishers and funding bodies.⁵

⁴ 6 out of the 11 repositories surveyed stored data relating to two or more disciplines. Table 2 is therefore a count of references made in relation to a given discipline.

⁵ Examples of current projects examining the use of metadata and PIDs for repositories include FREYA, <https://www.project-freya.eu/en/about/mission> [accessed 9 February 2022] and DataCite Commons, <https://blog.datacite.org/power-of-pids/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

3.1.3 Support during the Data Lifecycle

The support offered at different parts of the data-storage life cycle also varied greatly by organisation. All 14 respondents reported that they provided support to users in at least two stages of the data life cycle, with six organisations providing support across all eight stages of it. Nearly all offered support in curating meta(data) and facilitating the discovery of data and/or metadata (see figure 1). Most respondents also offered support for the initial conceptualisation of research projects, access to data, and the collection and/or creation of research (meta)data.

Only half the respondents provided support for the initial use of data, and its subsequent reuse. A possible reason for this is that such support would require the provision of analytical services and/or related software, which may not be a priority for organisations focusing primarily on curation and data discovery.

Figure 1. Overview of the organisations providing support at different stages of the data lifecycle. The organisations (n=14) were able to choose any number of alternatives. Full descriptions of the stages can be found in the questionnaire in Appendix 2.

Regarding curation, respondents were asked what level of curation they perform and were given the option to select one or more of the following responses: 'no curation and distribute content as deposited'; 'basic curation by briefly checking the data and adding basic metadata'; 'enhanced curation by converting

data to new formats and enhancing documentation'; 'data-level curation by further editing deposited data for accuracy'.⁶

Most respondents reported performing a combination of the above curation levels, with only five respondents selecting one level. The most common choice was enhanced curation, followed closely by basic curation (see figure 2). Six respondents reported providing data level curation, although five of these selected additional levels. A further two organisations indicated that they perform no curation for some data in their collection, alongside higher levels of curation for other parts of their collection.

Figure 2. Counts of organisations performing different levels of curation. The organisations (n=14) were able to choose any number of alternatives. Full descriptions of the types can be found in the questionnaire in Appendix 2.

⁶ CoreTrustSeal applicants are also asked what level of curation they provide (see CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board, 2019a.)

3.2 TDR Certification, Data Discovery, Metadata Provision and Citation

The majority of repositories surveyed (excluding the three organisations who did not meet our definition of a repository) held some form of TDR certification; eight had CoreTrustSeal certification, one had ISO 27001 certification and two were uncertified (see figure 3 below). The three service providers who did not meet our definition of a digital repository would not be eligible for CoreTrustSeal certification as they do not provide long-term digital preservation.

Figure 3. Certifications of the repositories (n=11). The repositories were able to choose more than one certificate, but each of them only mentioned one.

Certification status is also used to break down the results relayed in table 3. Areas covered in table 3 include whether the repository/organisation had a re3data⁷ record, whether PIDs were assigned to data, the availability of guidance for depositors on the required data and metadata formats, the availability of

⁷ Re3data: <https://www.re3data.org/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

metadata via other resource discovery services, the provision of model citations or citation guidelines, and whether the repository/organisation had an OAI-PMH⁸ endpoint.

Metadata provision, citation and related information by organisation						
	re3data record	PID use	Depositor guidelines on required data and metadata formats	Metadata availability via other resource discovery services	Model citation or guidelines provided to users	OAI-PMH endpoint
Repo 1	X	X	X	X	X	X
Repo 2	X	X	X	X	X	X
Repo 3	X	X	X	X	X	X
Repo 4	X	X	X		X	
Repo 5	X	X	X	X	X	
Repo 6	X	X	X	X	X	X
Repo 7	X	X	X	X	X	
Repo 8	X	X	X	X	X	X
Repo 9	X	X	X	X	X	X
Repo 10		X	X	X	X	X
Repo 11	X	X	X			X
Org 1			No metadata	No metadata		No metadata
Org 2			X		X	
Org 3		X	X		X	

Table 3. Certification status and other selected features of participating organisations. Non-certified organisations are highlighted in blue.

With the exception of one of the non-repository service providers, all respondents reported having a data catalogue to enable data discovery. The organisation without a data catalogue focused on providing access to a single indicator, thus having no need for a data catalogue. Two organisations used Dataverse⁹, while the rest had their own search and discovery solution. However, there were marked differences between respondents in terms of the availability of metadata via other resource discovery services, the use of OAI-PMH Endpoints and repository/organisational listing on re3data.

In terms of the latter, re3data is a search registry designed to facilitate the discovery of various data repositories by different types of users, such as researchers, publishers, and scholarly institutions. A

⁸ Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting: <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

⁹ Dataverse: <https://dataverse.org/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

significant number of respondents, 10 out of 14, were listed on re3data, with all certified repositories having re3data records. As re3data is targeted at data repositories, other service providers may make use of broader organisation identifier systems such as ROR¹⁰.

Persistent identifiers were used by the majority of respondents. DOI¹¹ was the most common PID system in use, with all 11 repositories using it (see figure 4). Three of the repositories used URN¹² in addition to DOI (with two of them using Handle¹³ as a third PID system). Out of the three non-repository organisations, one used URN (which was their sole provider of PIDs); the remaining two non-repository organisations indicated that they did not use PIDs.

Figure 4. Pids used by the organisations (n=14). The services were able to choose any number of alternatives.

¹⁰ Research Organization Registry, <https://ror.org/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

¹¹ Digital Object Identifier System: <https://doi.org> [accessed 9 February 2022]

¹² Technopedia - Uniform Resource Name <https://www.techopedia.com/definition/5612/uniform-resource-name-urn> [accessed 9 February 2022]

¹³ Handle.Net Registry: <http://www.handle.net/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

All 11 repositories (and two of the three non-repository organisations) provided guidance to depositors regarding required data and metadata formats. The organisation that did not provide such guidance did not rely on depositors for data and thus would have no need to provide it.

Nine repositories reported that their metadata was available through resource discovery services such as B2FIND, CLARIN VLO, or CESSDA Data Catalogue. Just over half of these repositories also had an OAI-PMH endpoint. On the other hand, none of the non-repository organisations had an OAI-PMH endpoint, despite all three providing at least one service that could potentially benefit from it.

As mentioned earlier, the differences in metadata provision, data discovery mechanisms and other related information appear to be distinguishable according to certification status, with those repositories holding CoreTrustSeal certification providing the most complete information pertaining in all of the different areas covered in table 3. TDR certification also appeared to play a role in the provision of policies, licences and legal information provided by the different organisations.

Finally, 11 of the respondents (repositories and non-repository service providers) supported data citation by providing a sample citation or citation instructions. Out of the repositories, four provided machine-actionable sample citations for individual datasets and four provided non-machine-actionable sample citations (see table 4). Two repositories provided general citations to be adapted depending on the data used. Two repositories that provided specific sample citations also provided additional citation guidelines or instructions for data users. Out of the non-repositories, one did not provide any citation support while two of them provided specific sample citations for individual datasets.

Citation support within sample				
	Machine-actionable specific citation (e.g. Bibtex, RIS) for each dataset	Sample citation for each dataset	General sample citation	Citation guidelines/instructions
Repositories	4	4	2	2
Non-repositories	0	2	0	0

Table 4. Citation support provided by respondents (n=14) to data users.

3.3 Policies, Licences and Legal information

With regard to the provision of outward-facing information, respondents were asked to provide links (or the text) for the following: repository mission statement; business continuity/succession plans (for (meta)data and other repository services); preservation policies, procedures or plans; legal and ethical information; rights information, licence lists and/or other licence information; metadata and data versioning policies; and service processes and workflow descriptions or diagrams.

All 14 respondents had a mission statement. A closer examination of the statements revealed differences in the content and length, although there were similarities between them, particularly amongst the certified repositories. All 11 repositories and one non-repository service provider mentioned providing access to or preserving data in the statement, which is expected in CoreTrustSeal Requirement 1¹⁴. Whilst the two non-repository service providers that did not mention this did not provide preservation service, their organisations did facilitate access to stored digital objects. Five of the respondents (all repositories) explicitly mentioned providing support to researchers, three repositories and one non-repository service provider said they conducted research, and one repository and one non-repository service provider mentioned the FAIR principles in the statement.

¹⁴ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board 2019b.

Policies, plans, licences and legal information by organisation						
	Business continuity or succession plan	Preservation policy	Legal and ethical information	Rights information and licences	Metadata and data versioning policy	Service processes, workflow descriptions
Repo 1	X	X	X	X	X	X
Repo 2	X	X	X	X	X	X
Repo 3	X	X	X	X	X	X
Repo 4		X		X		
Repo 5		X	X	X	X	X
Repo 6	X	X	X	X	X	X
Repo 7	X	X	X			
Repo 8	X	X	X	X	X	X
Repo 9	X	X		X		
Repo 10					X	
Repo 11			X			
Org 1	X		X	X		
Org 2			X	X	X	X
Org 3	X					

Table 5. Policies, licences and legal information of participating organisations. Non-certified organisations are highlighted in blue.

As can be seen in table 5 above, nine respondents had a business continuity plan as well as a preservation policy, procedure or plan in place. Ten of the respondents provided legal and ethical information, ten of them offered rights information and/or licences, eight had metadata and data versioning policies in place, and seven provided descriptions of service processes or workflows.

As CoreTrustSeal certification requires evidence on preservation, versioning, rights and other related information, it is not surprising that the majority of certified organisations had these plans and policies in place. Many of the non-certified organisations also provided some form of legal and/or ethical information, although the provision of other policies and documents varied, with none of the non-certified repositories having a Preservation policy. However, some of the non-certified organisations noted in their answers that they were in the process of drafting such plans and policies.

It should be noted that the respondents interpreted the policies and information in various ways. For instance, when asked to provide links to their legal and ethical information, the participating repositories provided links to documentation covering general terms and conditions, legal disclosures (for their website), governance information (for the repository and/or host institution), legal requirements for researchers, information on ethical boards, privacy policies (for site use) and data protection for research participants. Appendix 4 provides a detailed breakdown of the types of documentation provided.

The variation in information may in part be due to the wording of the questions which did not always specify the type(s) of policies and information that the survey was asking about in great detail.

Nonetheless, the results are indicative of the variation between organisations in terms of the scope, and the level of detail of the information provided to users and stakeholders, and the different interpretations of what constitutes legal and ethical information. Community consensus on the definition of 'legal' and 'ethical information' is an important point because, with the move towards actionable machine-actionable data management plans, such definitions will need to be defined in order to develop a controlled vocabulary and/or metadata schema to relay such information in a structured format.¹⁵ The distinction as to what constitutes legal and ethical information also plays a role in the development of standards, although this will be expanded upon in the concluding remarks.

Similarly, the respondents' interpretations of service processes and workflow diagrams differed considerably. The purpose of requesting this information was to examine how many respondents had publicly available, documented workflows which is a necessary Requirement for CoreTrustSeal certification (see R12 'Workflows'), with diagrams also being recommended in R0 'Context' and R9 'Documented storage procedures'.¹⁶ Respondents provided links to a range of documentation such as data sharing instructions for depositors, organisation charts and repository terms and conditions.

3.4 Preservation, Technical Infrastructure and Data Integrity

The survey also examined the preservation approach, technical infrastructure and the data integrity and security measures employed by respondents' organisations. Respondents were asked whether their organisation employed any of the common digital preservation strategies e.g., format and schema migration and/or emulation (see table 6). All three of the non-repository service providers selected 'Can't say or N/A' which was expected, as they do not provide long-term digital preservation. Three of the repositories selected 'Can't say or N/A'; seven of the repositories selected 'format and schema migration' and one repository selected 'both'. It is worth noting that two of the three repositories that selected 'Can't say or N/A' were not certified. Upon further examination by the authors, the certified repository (where the representative selected 'Can't say or N/A') stated in their CoreTrustSeal application that they "may" employ a format migration approach to preserving depositor data. However, neither of the non-certified repositories (where the representative answered 'Can't say or N/A') had a preservation policy, which potentially suggests that format migration or emulation is not employed.

¹⁵ See, for instance, Simms et al. 2017.

¹⁶ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board 2019a.

Repository approach to active preservation				
	Format and schema migration approach <i>only</i>	Emulation approach <i>only</i>	<i>Both</i> approaches in use	Can't say or N/A
Number of repositories	8 repositories*	0 repositories	1 repository	2 repositories

Table 6. Repository approach to active preservation (n=11). *The certified repository that answered 'Can't say or n/a' has been included in this column as it was determined by the authors (after reviewing their CoreTrustSeal application) that they engaged in format migration.

Respondents were also asked who provides their technical infrastructure. The responses to this question were more varied, with two out of the three non-repository service providers and four of the repositories indicating that their technical infrastructure was provided by 'the organisation/the repository itself'. The remaining non-repository service provider and one repository indicated that their technical infrastructure was provided by 'a third party (outsourced)'. Of the remaining six repositories, three selected that their technical infrastructure was provided by 'the host organisation' and the other three repositories indicated that they 'shared responsibility' with regards to their technical infrastructure.¹⁷ Figure 5 below provides an overview of the answers selected by all 14 respondents.

¹⁷ All three repositories that selected 'shared responsibility' stated that responsibility was shared between the repository and the hosting organisation.

Figure 5. The bodies providing the technical infrastructure of participating organisations (n=14).

The final topic explored by the survey concerned the data integrity and security measures employed by the responding organisations. None of the non-repository service providers had any integrity and security measures in place as they do not preserve data; thus, the responses reported below are from repositories only.

Some of the repositories did reference specific methods for ensuring data integrity at various points during the research data lifecycle (pre-ingest through to dissemination). Such methods included: normalisation; checksum generation; and bitstream copying, among others. However, due to significant variation in the methods reported, and the terminology used to describe such methods, checksum generation was the only feasible area which could be tabulated (see table 7 below).

Use of checksums within sample						
	Not in use	Checksums (type not specified)	Md5	Sha-128	Sha-256	Unf
Repo 1			X			
Repo 2	X					
Repo 3				X		
Repo 4			X	X		
Repo 5					X	
Repo 6			X	X		
Repo 7	X					
Repo 8		X				
Repo 9			X			X
Repo 10	X					
Repo 11	X					

Table 7. Use of checksums by the repositories in the sample (excluding non-repositories). Non-certified repositories are highlighted in blue.

As can be seen in table 7 above, four out of the 11 repositories in our sample did not use checksums, with two of the repositories being CoreTrustSeal certified. Whilst this may appear concerning, it is important to note that the use of checksums is only a *recommendation*, rather than a *requirement* for CoreTrustSeal certification. Furthermore, while it was possible for the authors to ascertain whether checksums were in use, it was not possible to ascertain the exact stage at which the checksums were applied e.g., Ingest, staging, dissemination and so forth.

The variation in the data integrity methods used by the repositories in our sample, and the differences in the terminology used to describe such methods (even amongst the certified repositories) does raise the question of whether further work is needed to define the terminology used to describe data integrity measures. However, due to our small sample size, it is not possible to make direct assertions as to whether such work is required.

4. Discussion

Although the results of this survey are not generalisable to the wider repository landscape due to the small sample size, the findings do indicate that the trust landscape of SSHOC organisations varies a great deal. The results also suggest that future work on the harmonisation of the repository landscape regarding repository practice and certification is needed, with one of these areas being data discovery and metadata provision. As discussed in Section 3.2, many of the organisations surveyed had records on re3data, with all but one of the certified repositories having re3data records. Conversely, only one of the two non-certified repositories and none of the three non-repository service providers had a re3data record. Whilst it is possible that the organisations without re3data records may be listed on alternative registries such as ROR, it does suggest that certification may play a role in registry use for the respondents in our survey. However, further work would be needed to identify whether certification played a role in registry use within the wider digital preservation community. Registry use is of particular importance should the ongoing work concerning PID graphs¹⁸ prove fruitful, as repositories and wider data service providers would need to be listed on registries and assigned a globally unique identifier to be included in a PID graph.¹⁹

With reference to the use of persistent identifiers, although most of the organisations indicated using PIDs, two of them did not. Of the two organisations, one would be classed as a metadata registry and the other a research foundation. The latter has a third-party agreement with an external, non-certified repository to store the data it generates.²⁰ Given both organisations provide metadata concerning publications and/or datasets, the lack of PID use for said metadata is concerning given the community consensus to commit to the FAIR principles²¹. Whilst further research is needed to examine the use of PIDs and adherence to other community standards by non-repository service providers, the results of this survey suggest the potential need for the certification of non-repository data services which is currently being examined by the CoreTrustSeal.²²

A reassuringly high number of our respondents provided guidance to data depositors on the required metadata and data formats. Similarly, a fair number of them also provided machine-actionable, third-party metadata. However, there were clear differences between the certified and non-certified

¹⁸ See 'The FREYA Project', <https://www.project-freya.eu/Plone/en> [accessed 9 February 2022] and Fenner & Aryani 2019 for examples of ongoing work.

¹⁹ DataCite Commons, <https://blog.datacite.org/power-of-pids/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

²⁰ The third-party repository does assign PIDs to the data it stores for the Research Foundation.

²¹ F1 of the FAIR Data Principles states: "(meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier", GO FAIR - FAIR Principles: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

²² CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board 2020.

repositories in basic metadata provision, data discovery and citation practices. This is particularly notable when looking at OAI-PMH endpoints and the availability of metadata via discovery services. This, again, highlights the potential benefits (at least for our sample) of certification and its potential in raising repository standards.

The possible role that certification played in adherence to community standards can also be seen in the provision of policies, licences and legal information. There were marked differences between the certified and non-certified repositories in the (public) availability of preservation policies and documentation regarding service processes and/or workflows. The differing interpretations of what constituted licences and/or legal policies outlined in Appendix 3 suggests that further community work may be needed on defining the terminology, and the content of such policies.

The significant number of 'Can't say' responses to the question regarding preservation approach taken demonstrates that there should be more transparency around the levels of curation and preservation, both internally and externally. This particularly applies to non-certified repositories and non-repository service providers, most of which responded 'Can't say'. The variation in respondents' technical infrastructures suggests the need for increased transparency surrounding the services that are insourced and/or outsourced. This is particularly important when undergoing formal assessment for TDR certification (e.g. the CoreTrustSeal). Transparency around such arrangements helps establish trust in a given repository and provides evidence that Principles such as FAIR are being adhered to. A possible recommendation is that further clarification could be provided by TDR standards bodies (such as the CoreTrustSeal) as to the expected degree of information applicants need to provide regarding third-party agreements that they are engaged in.

Finally, the variation in the terminology used, and the methods employed by the repositories to ensure data integrity hints at another possible area for further work. Such variation is related to the fact that there are few, if any, community-agreed minima on what measures a data-holding organisation should have in place, despite CoreTrustSeal requiring information about the storage and technical infrastructure of applicants. The difficulty in obtaining this information for the purposes of the report also highlights the need for a community-wide discussion on the minimum level of information that repositories must provide regarding the integrity measures employed.

5. Conclusion

The conclusions that can be drawn from this report are that further work is needed in reaching community-agreed terminology, typology of services and essential information provided by data-holding organisations. Based on the results, it appears that being CoreTrustSeal-certified improves the documentation and policies on the organisation's processes and activities as well as the provision of information to users and stakeholders.

While there are many organisations for which CoreTrustSeal certification is a good fit, there are also essential services around research data that do not fit the definition of a data repository because they only offer access to metadata or house their own data.

The definition of a data repository in the context of SSHOC T8.2 was outlined in the foreword. It is similar to but more restrictive than the CoreTrustSeal's definition of a repository, which defines them as organisations that "preserve, manage, and provide access to *many types of digital materials in a variety of formats*".²³ The CoreTrustSeal definition further states that "[m]aterials in online repositories are curated to enable search, discovery, and reuse. There must be sufficient control for the digital material to be authentic, reliable, accessible and usable on a continuing basis."

Based on SSHOC T8.2's definition, organisations that only provide metadata do not qualify as data repositories, even if they provide data discovery services. Although the CoreTrustSeal definition does not preclude these types of organisations, the requirement for sufficient control over the digital material as well as the focus of the CoreTrustSeal requirements²⁴ on data practically means that organisations that do not preserve data have limited options for certification. This is also the case for organisations that preserve data but do not provide any metadata to enable their discovery and reuse.

As existing TDR certification schemes are not applicable to all organisations providing data services, there is a need for other certification or assessment solutions. The analysis of the survey contributes to the ongoing work of organisations like the CoreTrustSeal which are currently examining whether there is a desire / need for organisations beyond 'traditional data repositories' to be certified.²⁵ Many organisations providing data services might also benefit from undertaking a self-assessment against certification requirements without going for full certification, as practices, documentation and policies are often

²³ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board 2019c. The definition originates from the CASRAI Research Data Management Glossary (<https://casrai.org/rdm-glossary/> [accessed 9 February 2022]).

²⁴ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board 2019a.

²⁵ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board 2020.

improved when organisations become aware of the aspects required for becoming a trusted digital repository.

These issues are related to a wider discussion on whether a certification scheme should even exist for all types of organisations and services, and what the minimum requirements for them would be. The discussion is beyond the scope of this report but should be addressed in the future in projects focusing on (trusted) digital repositories and their certification.

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7. Appendixes

Appendix 1: Methodology

The responses were collected via Google Forms between 28 June and 10 September 2021, and the invitation to participate was disseminated to all organisations participating in SSHOC. The organisations were also encouraged to share the survey link to other relevant bodies. The survey yielded 18 responses altogether, but some of them came from different employees of the same entity. These duplicate responses were combined into single ones resulting in 14 unique responses.

Appendix 2: Survey Questionnaire

Data Services - Repositories and Beyond

This informal questionnaire seeks brief initial responses and links to public information from any body that sees itself as offering services around (meta)data in any part of the research data lifecycle. We are seeking one or two sentences describing the service perspective on the item along with links to related information.

This questionnaire is part of SSHOC T8.2: Trust & Quality Assurance. The responses will be used to examine the applicability of the CoreTrustSeal to various data services. They will also be used to provide a broad perspective on the perception of services with a view to describing different types of service and how they can integrate and interoperate in federated research infrastructures, such as the EOSC.

Please respond for the full range of services offered by your organisation/repository. The definition of services is intended to be broad with a view to generating more granular definitions in the future. If you represent more than one organisation, only respond on behalf of one of them and indicate which one in the first question below.

1. Your name and organisation/repository

2. Does your organisation hold and provide access to... data / metadata?

Yes

No

3. Briefly describe the types of data and or metadata collections your organisation holds.

4. If your organisation has Re3data record, please provide a link to it here.

5. If your organisation has attained any certifications or standard assessments (e.g CoreTrustSeal, ISO 27001), please list them here.

6. What is your organisation's mission statement, service definition or defined scope?

7. Does your organisation address data and metadata at a generalist or specialist level?

Generalist

Specialist

Can't say or N/A

8. If you address data at a specialist level, which disciplines or domains?

9. Please tick all parts of the data lifecycle where your organisation offers related support.

Concept: Services around the initial conceptualisation, proposal and funding for research projects.

Generate: Services around the collection or creation of research (meta) data

Use: Services that support research project in their initial use of data including analytics, software etc.

Deposit: The transfer of data from the active research phase into longer term storage, curation or preservation system. Including any appraisal and selection processes or standards.

Curate: Curate (meta) data to ensure standards compliance and expected levels of quality.

Discovery: The provision of resource discovery systems or of harvestable data or metadata so that it can be pushed to, or harvested by others.

Access: Providing access to data including authentication/authorisation, permission-based workflows, licence agreement etc. Including any safe room or secure remote access systems if offered, e.g. for sensitive data access.

ReUse: Services that support the reuse phase of the lifecycle including any analytics services, software.

10. What type of curation does your organisation perform?

A. No curation (content distributed as deposited)

B. Basic curation – e.g., brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation

C. Enhanced curation – e.g., conversion to new formats, enhancement of documentation

D. Data-level curation – as in C above, but with additional editing of deposited data for accuracy

11. Please provide link(s) to your organisation's metadata requirements and data format requirements for data depositors.

12. If your organisation uses a persistent identifier (PID) for data, which one?

DOI

URN

ARK

Handle

No PIDs used

Other

13. Please provide a link to your organisation's data catalogue.

14. Is your organisation's metadata available via other resource discovery services (e.g. B2FIND, CLARIN VLO, CESSDA catalogue)?

Yes

No

Can't say or N/A

15. Please provide a link to your organisation's OAI-PMH endpoint.

16. How does your organisation support data citation? Please provide, for example, a model citation or a link to citation guidelines.

17. Does your organisation have a business continuity or a succession plan for your (meta)data and services if you cease to exist or change mission?

Yes

No

Can't say or N/A

18. Please provide link(s) to your organisation's legal and ethical information.

19. Please provide link(s) to your rights information, licence lists and/or licences.
20. Please provide link(s) to your service processes and workflow descriptions or diagrams.
21. Please provide link(s) to your metadata and data versioning policy.
22. Do you take a format and schema migration approach to and/or do you use emulation for active preservation?
- Format and schema migration approach
 - Emulation
 - Both
 - Neither
 - Can't say or N/A
23. Please provide link(s) to your preservation policy, procedure or plan
24. Who provides the technical infrastructure of your organisation/repository?
- The organisation/repository itself
 - The host organisation
 - A third party (outsourced)
 - Can't say or N/A
25. What measures do you take to ensure data integrity?
26. What security measures do you take to protect the (meta)data you hold?
27. You can leave your comments or feedback about the survey here.

Appendix 3: Categorisation of Responses by Types of Data and Metadata

Categorisation of responses by types of data and metadata held		
Category	Direct quotation*	Types reported
(Research) Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Survey research data..." • "Primary and secondary research data in a wide variety of formats" • "Data ranges from text and spreadsheets, to... remote sensing and 3D imagery" • "Rectangular data from mainly the social sciences and humanities" • "Survey data as Scientific Use Files" • "Scientific datasets (covering all scientific disciplines with an emphasis on Social Sciences and Humanities)" • "Datasets" • "Data from various scientific disciplines" • "Financial data" • "(Historical) financial data" • "geographical databases" • "Social science qualitative and quantitative data" • "Survey data of salaries by occupation" • "data of Minimum Wage rates" • "coded data of Collective Bargaining Agreements" • "Living wage data" 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey data • Primary data • Secondary data • Textual data • Spreadsheets • Remote sensing [data/datasets] • 3d Imagery [type unspecified] • Rectangular data [type unspecified] Scientific Use Files • Datasets • Financial data • Geographical databases • Scientific Datasets • Quantitative data • Qualitative data • Coded data

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “mainly quantitative social science data” • “mostly quantitative survey data and its documentation in the field of social sciences” • “Mainly data... from social sciences, humanities, health science, earth and environmental sciences” 	
Metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Metadata which describes the data (covering both technical aspects and subject matter)” • “associated metadata [of the stored surveys] according to the Data Documentation Initiative” • “Dublin Core + other specific metadata schemes [schemas]” • “metadata: dc core, relational metadata between papers and research data.” • “(extended) Dublin Core metadata, relational metadata between research articles and research data” • “Library catalogues and collections; bibliographical” • “metadata about the studies, collected online” • “metadata at study, dataset, and data file levels” • “metadata describing them [quantitative social science datasets]” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical metadata • Subject metadata • Metadata schemas <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o DDI o Dublin Core • Relational metadata • Library catalogues • Library collections • Bibliographical [metadata] • Object Metadata

(Other) Digital Objects		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • API • Geographical Information Systems [type unspecified]
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* The wording of responses was not altered, except to separate sentences that referred to both data and metadata. Where separation resulted in a loss of meaning, additional wording was added in (square) parentheses to indicate wording added by the authors.

Appendix 4: Legal and Ethical Documentation Provided by Organisations

Legal and ethical documentation provided by organisations		
	Documentation Referenced	Areas covered
Repo 1	Governance [Webpage]	<i>Webpage provided links to documentation covering the following areas:</i> Strategic planning; management committees; period reporting; funding (of the repository)
Repo 2	CoreTrustSeal Application [document]	<i>The CoreTrustSeal application covered:</i> The repository's provider of legal advice; legal and ethical standards pertaining to the research data stored; legal information provided to the depositor; user misconduct / non-compliance with user agreement(s)
Repo 3	Legal Disclosure [Webpage]	<i>Webpage outlined the Legal terms pertaining to the repository's portal:</i> Deposit agreement; processing of personal data (deposit and end-user); privacy policy; legal liability (pertaining to the data deposited); intellectual property rights.
Repo 4	None	<i>The repository response was: "None"</i>
Repo 5	Legal Disclosure [Webpage]	<i>The webpage addressed the following areas:</i>

		Accuracy of information provided (on the repositories website); content of external links; copyright for materials and/or objects produced by the repository and its host institution; data protection (in short).
	<i>Data Protection Policy</i> [Webpage]	<i>The webpage addressed the following areas:</i> User Rights; transference of data; usage statistics; mailing lists and contact preferences; data derived from social media; content of external links.
Repo 6	General terms and conditions [Document]	<i>Document covered the following areas in relation to the services provided by the repository:</i> Assignment and completion of work; liability; payment conditions; intellectual property rights; and dissemination of intellectual property.
	Privacy statement [Document]	<i>Document provided information on the following areas in relation to conducting research:</i> Use of data; Purpose (for processing data); Legal basis (for processing data); types of data collected; information security measures; retention of data; third party access to data; rights (of the data subject)
Repo 7	Guidance for Depositors [Webpage]	<i>Webpage provided links to further webpages covering the following topics:</i> Data Management Plans; Information for Research Participants; Archival Data; Curation of data; Depositor Checklists; Rights of Data Subjects; Research Ethics; User Guide (for a specific portal)
Repo 8	Ethics Policy [Webpage]	<i>The webpage provided information on the legal</i>

		<p><i>requirements affecting research in relation to the following areas:</i></p> <p>The collection and/or analysis of special category and/or sensitive data for the purposes of research; the process for obtaining ethical approval from the national ethics body; obtaining consent from research participants; animal testing.</p>
	<p>Personal Data in Research [Webpage]</p>	<p><i>The webpage provided further guidance on research material that contained the personal information of participants, which covered the following points:</i></p> <p>Principles of data protection, legal basis for the processing of personal data; definition of sensitive and/or special category data; direct and indirect personal data; identification of participants; the storage of personal data.</p>
Repo 9	[Missing data]	<p><i>No response was recorded for this question.</i></p>
Repo 10	Ethics Board Information [Webpage]	<p><i>Webpage provided brief information on the purposes of the internal Ethics Board which covered:</i></p> <p>Research Ethics; data managements</p>
Repo 11	<p>Legal Disclosure [Webpage]</p> <p>Code of Ethics [Document]</p>	<p><i>Webpage provided information concerning the repository which covered:</i></p> <p>Management board (of the repository); responsibility for content; responsibility for the content of external links; intellectual property rights.</p> <p><i>The information contained within the document concerned the conduct of researchers based at the host institution for the</i></p>

		<i>repository. The areas covered in the document included: The operational definition of good practice and misconduct; disciplinary investigation, management and resolution;</i>
Org 1	None	<i>The response included a link to the website but there was no separate legal and ethical information provided.</i>
Org 2	Conditions of use [Webpage]	<i>The webpage provided general information on the use of the service and metadata.</i>
Org 3	None	<i>The response was: "N/A - Under development".</i>

Non-certified organisations are highlighted in blue.

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